

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence for Pedagogical Innovation in Stem Education: A Case from Kwara State Schools

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Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) are rapidly reshaping educational practices, and stakeholders in the education sector are increasingly embracing their transformative potential. Despite this progress, integration in many contexts has been limited mainly to social interaction, with minimal pedagogical application. This study investigated the integration of ILS as a means of leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) for pedagogical innovation among STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State, focusing on teachers' awareness, accessibility, and utilization of AI-based instructional technologies, as well as demographic differences in usage. A descriptive survey design was employed with a sample of 327 STEM teachers drawn from public and private secondary schools through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a validated and reliable questionnaire (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.87) and analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-tests, and one-way ANOVA. The findings revealed that teachers demonstrated substantially high awareness of ILS and AI tools (overall mean = 1.98), average accessibility (overall mean = 2.22), and limited utilization (overall mean = 2.37). Significant differences were found between public and private school teachers, with public school teachers reporting higher usage, while no significant gender difference was observed. However, subject discipline was found to significantly influence both access and utilization of AI tools. The study concluded that while STEM teachers are aware of AI's potential, infrastructural barriers, limited technical support, and modest practical application hinder full integration. It recommended targeted training,

Keywords:
Intelligent Learning Systems, Artificial Intelligence, Pedagogical Innovation, STEM Education and Secondary School Teachers.

Introduction

Education remains the cornerstone of national development, and the need for high-quality, inclusive, and innovative educational systems is more pressing than ever. In Nigeria, conventional pedagogical approaches, typically teacher-centered and dependent on outdated methods of content delivery, have proven inadequate in meeting the demands of twenty-first-century

learners. As societies advance toward a digital and knowledge-driven global economy, educational systems must evolve by adopting intelligent technologies that nurture creativity, critical thinking, and individualized learning experiences. The most promising development in this context is the incorporation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into teaching and learning through

Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS). (Ibrahim et al.,2025) Intelligent Learning Systems are AI-powered educational technologies designed to mimic human intelligence in order to personalize learning, automate assessments, and deliver real-time feedback (Jimba-Na 'Allah et al 2024). These systems can process extensive data on students' learning patterns and tailor the content to meet their specific needs.

In the Nigerian context, where education faces persistent challenges such as overcrowded classrooms, inadequate teaching staff, and limited access to quality learning materials, the ILS presents a transformative solution capable of addressing these systemic issues and improving learning outcomes. (Jacob & Josiah,2021) The use of AI in education extends beyond automation; it facilitates meaningful pedagogical innovation. AI technologies assist educators in developing adaptive learning pathways, identifying students' learning gaps, and creating engaging and interactive content (Bali et al., 2024). AI can also support functions such as language translation, speech recognition, and personalized content delivery, making education more accessible and inclusive particularly for students in Nigeria's linguistically and culturally diverse regions. For instance, intelligent tutoring systems and AI-based chatbots can complement conventional teaching by providing continuous support outside of the classroom. (Okunade, 2024). Moreover, the effectiveness of AI integration may be influenced by various factors, including school ownership (whether public or private), gender of the educators, and t subject discipline, particularly within STEM fields such as biology, chemistry, and physics. These moderating variables are important to consider, as they can shape teachers' access,

perception, and utilization of Intelligent Learning Systems in their pedagogical practice. Understanding these nuances will provide a clearer picture of the opportunities and challenges faced in different educational settings and among diverse groups of educators.

Despite its vast potential, the implementation of Intelligent Learning Systems in Nigeria is still in the early stages. Obstacles, such as inadequate digital infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and concerns about data privacy and equity, need to be systematically (Okunade, 2024). This study explored how AI-driven intelligent learning systems can be harnessed to foster pedagogical innovation in Nigerian education. It aimed to assess the current landscape, identify effective practices, and recommend strategies for successful integration, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive, responsive, and technologically advanced educational framework. Therefore, the objectives of this study are as follows:

1. investigate the awareness level of STEM secondary school teachers on artificial intelligence in Kwara State;
2. Assess the access level of secondary school STEM teachers towards artificial intelligence in Kwara State;
3. examined the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers in secondary schools in Kwara State;
4. examined the difference between school ownership and the use of artificial intelligence in by secondary schools STEM teachers in Kwara State;
5. determined the influence of gender on the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers in secondary school in Kwara State;

6. determined the influence of subject discipline on access level to artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State;
7. determined the influence of subject discipline on the use of artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of awareness of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools among STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State?
2. How accessible are Artificial Intelligence technologies for pedagogical use in STEM classrooms within secondary schools in Kwara State?
3. What is the extent of utilization of AI-driven Intelligent Learning Systems by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State to support teaching and learning?

Research Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the usage of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools between school ownership by secondary schools STEM teachers in Kwara State;
2. There is no significant difference in gender on the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers in secondary schools in Kwara State;
3. There is no significant difference in subject discipline on access level to artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State
4. There is no significant difference in subject discipline on use of artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State

Literature Review

Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) represent one of the most promising applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, offering adaptive and personalized instruction that can significantly improve student learning outcomes. By using advanced algorithms and machine learning, these systems move beyond conventional teaching approaches, aligning content delivery with individual student needs while also addressing accessibility and ethical issues (Oladipo et al., 2024). For students in Nigeria, there is a growing optimism that AI can transform learning, particularly in STEM fields, though concerns remain about technical challenges, data privacy, and the adequacy of teacher training to support meaningful adoption (Onyezere, 2024). Samuel & Salisu (2023) emphasize that AI applications such as virtual laboratories, adaptive platforms, and automated administrative tools directly address key challenges in Nigerian education, including poor infrastructure and shortages of qualified teachers. By generating data-driven insights, AI expands access to quality STEM education and sustains student interest in STEM-related careers. These tools not only enrich pedagogy but also promote inclusion by supporting students with diverse learning needs. For example, automated assessment systems and adaptive feedback mechanisms streamline grading, improve efficiency, and foster higher engagement (Kumar, 2024).

Evidence points to the strong impact of AI-driven adaptive learning on student achievement. Okunade (2024) reports that personalization enhances engagement and performance, while Sari and Efron (2024) demonstrate how data-driven insights enable teachers to provide more precise interventions. In the same line, Suntharalingam (2024)

underscores that Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) not only raise student satisfaction but also strengthen teacher effectiveness, fostering a more efficient and supportive classroom environment. In Nigerian contexts, Adenubi and Samuel (2024) report that predictive modelling and analytics can identify at-risk learners, allowing for timely support that improves retention and academic success. At the institutional level, AI tools are also transforming administrative and curricular processes. Studies show that intelligent platforms foster inclusivity through approaches such as Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and gamification, which enhance student motivation and deepen STEM learning (Drigas & Kefalis, 2024). The Inclusive Science model further emphasizes embedding diversity, strengthening institutional support, and connecting students' social identities to their STEM learning experiences (Cobian et al., 2024). Together, these approaches demonstrate that AI is not just a teaching aid but a driver of systemic educational innovation.

Adoption in Nigeria remains uneven. Wahab et al. (2024) and Sunday et al. (2025) identify persistent challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, high costs, and limited digital literacy among teachers. Ethical concerns, including data privacy and algorithmic bias, also threaten equitable implementation. In addition, factors such as teacher attitudes, institutional support, gender, and geographical context shape the extent to which AI tools are embraced in schools (Okorieocha & Ugwunali, 2025). These findings highlight the importance of continuous professional development, robust policy frameworks, and participatory approaches that actively involve educators in decision-making (Olabiyi & Chinedu, 2025). Bali et al. (2024) provide a broad review of AI integration in Nigerian education, noting that while basic digital technologies are gaining ground, advanced systems such as intelligent tutoring,

robotics, and adaptive management platforms remain underutilized. This gap reveals the urgent need for Nigerian stakeholders to learn from global best practices while tailoring AI strategies to local socio-cultural realities (Makinde et al., 2025). A holistic approach that blends technical innovation with social and cultural sensitivity is critical for AI to fully realize its transformative potential in STEM education, ultimately improving teaching practices, learning outcomes, and long-term participation in STEM fields.

Methods

This study employed a descriptive survey design to investigate the integration of Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) for pedagogical innovation among STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State. The descriptive approach was considered appropriate as it allows for a systematic examination of teachers' current awareness, accessibility, and utilization of AI tools, providing baseline data to inform targeted interventions and policy development. A total of 327 STEM teachers from public and private secondary schools were selected using a stratified random sampling technique to ensure representation across gender, school type, and subject specialization. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, that assessing teachers' awareness, accessibility, and utilization of AI-based instructional technologies. The instrument demonstrated strong psychometric properties, with both face and construct validity established, and a high internal consistency reliability confirmed by a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87. For data analysis, descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, means, and standard deviations, were used to address the research questions, while inferential statistics,

specifically t-tests and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), were applied to test the hypotheses and examine demographic differences in usage patterns.

Results and Discussions

RQ1: What is the level of awareness of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools among STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State.

Table 1:
The level of awareness of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools among STEM secondary school teachers

Item	HA		MA		SA		NA		Mean
	F	F%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
I am familiar with the term "Intelligent Learning Systems" (ILS).	149	45.4%	134	40.9%	33	10.1%	11	3.4%	1.71
I understand how AI tools can be used to support teaching and learning.	89	27.1%	165	50.3%	59	18.0%	14	4.3%	1.99
I can identify examples of AI-powered tools used in education.	127	38.7%	171	52.1%	18	5.5%	11	3.4%	1.73
I am aware of AI applications that help personalize student learning.	96	29.3%	169	51.5%	56	17.1%	6	1.8%	1.91
I have heard of intelligent tutoring systems used in STEM classrooms.	73	22.3%	180	54.9%	57	17.4%	17	5.2%	2.06
I understand the potential of AI in transforming education.	70	21.3%	154	47.0%	99	30.2%	4	1.2%	2.11
I have attended training or workshops on AI in education.	95	29.0%	160	48.8%	63	19.2%	9	2.7%	1.96
I stay updated on current trends in educational technology and AI.	66	20.1%	155	47.3%	83	25.3%	23	7.0%	2.19
I am confident in explaining the benefits of AI in the classroom.	86	26.2%	158	48.2%	72	22.0%	11	3.4%	2.02
I am aware of government or institutional policies promoting AI in education.	65	19.8%	162	49.4%	88	26.8%	12	3.7%	2.14
Average mean									1.98.

The findings in Table 1 show that the level of awareness of Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) and other AI tools among STEM secondary

school teachers in Kwara State was relatively average, with an overall mean of 1.98. The majority of teachers reported being familiar with

the term ILS (86.3%), identifying examples of AI-powered tools (90.8%), and being aware of AI applications that personalize learning (80.8%). Similarly, most teachers acknowledged understanding how AI can support teaching and learning (77.4%) and were aware of intelligent tutoring systems (77.2%). However, deeper awareness indicators reveal limitations. For instance, fewer teachers strongly understood AI's transformative potential in education (only 21.3% at high awareness), and awareness of government or institutional policies promoting AI in education was lower (69.2% agreed, but fewer at high awareness). Additionally, only a modest proportion stayed

updated on trends in AI trends (67.4%) or felt confident in explaining AI benefits (74.4%). Overall, while teachers demonstrate a good foundational awareness of AI concepts and tools, their practical understanding, policy awareness, and confidence in applying AI in pedagogy requires further strengthening through targeted professional development and institutional support. This finding is in line with (Okunade, 2024) and Adenubi and Samuel (2024)

RQ2: How accessible are Artificial Intelligence technologies for pedagogical use in STEM classrooms in secondary schools in Kwara State?

Table 2:

Accessibility Artificial Intelligence technologies for pedagogical use in STEM classrooms within secondary schools

Items	SA		A		D		SD		Mean
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
AI-based tools are available for use in my school.	88	26.8%	142	43.3%	85	25.9%	12	3.7%	2.06
I have access to the internet for using online AI resources.	70	21.3%	133	40.5%	91	27.7%	33	10.1%	2.27
My school provides digital devices (e.g., laptops, tablets) that can support AI tools.	69	21.0%	144	43.9%	97	29.6%	17	5.2%	2.19
There is adequate infrastructure (e.g., electricity, network) for using AI tools.	55	16.8%	132	40.2%	118	36.0%	22	6.7%	2.33
Educational software with AI features is made available to teachers.	105	32.0%	107	32.6%	87	26.5%	28	8.5%	2.12
I can easily access AI platforms suitable for my teaching needs.	57	17.4%	151	46.0%	106	32.3%	13	4.0%	2.23
I receive technical support for integrating AI into classroom instruction.	55	16.8%	112	34.1%	133	40.5%	27	8.2%	2.40
The school leadership encourages the use of AI tools in teaching.	69	21.0%	152	46.3%	79	24.1%	27	8.2%	2.20
I do not face financial barriers in accessing AI-based educational tools.	82	25.0%	130	39.6%	99	30.2%	16	4.9%	2.15
AI tools are easily incorporated into my lesson plans and classroom activities.	81	24.7%	119	36.3%	103	31.4%	24	7.3%	2.21
Average Mean									2.22

The results in Table 2 reveal that the accessibility of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies for pedagogical use in STEM classrooms within secondary schools in Kwara State is generally average. The overall average mean score of 2.22 suggests that teachers have limited but growing access to AI tools and resources. A large proportion of respondents agreed that AI-based tools were available in schools (70.1%), that they had access to the Internet (61.8%), and that digital devices are provided (64.9%), indicating some infrastructural support. However, challenges remain, as many teachers reported inadequate infrastructure, such as electricity and network connectivity (42.7% disagreed), insufficient technical support (48.7%

disagreed), and difficulty in incorporating AI tools into lesson plans (38.7% disagreed). Although school leadership encourage toward AI use (67.3% agreement), financial barriers and accessibility issues still exist. These findings imply that, while the foundation for AI adoption in STEM classrooms is present, infrastructural limitations, technical support gaps, and integration challenges hinder full accessibility and utilization. This finding is consistent with that of Adenubi and Samuel, (2024) and Makinde et al., (2025).

RQ:3 What is the extent of the utilization of AI-driven Intelligent Learning Systems by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State to support teaching and learning?

Table 3:
Utilization of AI-driven Intelligent Learning Systems by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State

Items	SA F %	A F %	D F %	SD F %	Mean
I use AI tools to assess student performance and give timely feedback.	45 13.7%	147 44.8%	113 34.5%	216 6.4%	2.34
incorporate AI-powered platforms in teaching STEM subjects.	51 15.5%	143 43.6%	124 37.8%	8 2.4%	2.27
I use Intelligent Learning Systems to identify students' strengths and weaknesses.	44 13.4%	130 39.6%	132 40.2%	206 6.1%	2.39
I personalize my teaching strategies based on data generated from AI tools.	47 14.3%	117 35.7%	138 42.1%	257 6.6%	2.43
I use AI-supported simulations or virtual labs to explain STEM concepts.	69 21.0%	124 37.8%	118 36.0%	164 9.9%	2.25
I apply AI tools to support differentiated instruction for students with varying abilities.	59 18.0%	118 36.0%	145 44.2%	5 1.5%	2.29
I analyze student learning patterns using AI analytics to inform instruction.	40 12.2%	102 31.1%	164 50.0%	21 6.4%	2.51
I use gamified learning platforms powered by AI to engage students.	50 15.2%	99 30.2%	158 48.2%	206 6.1%	2.45
I plan and deliver lessons that incorporate AI tools to enhance learning.	54 16.5%	107 32.6%	149 45.4%	175 5.2%	2.39
I collaborate with colleagues to explore and implement AI-driven teaching strategies in STEM education.	48 14.6%	127 38.7%	130 39.6%	226 7.1%	2.39
Average Mean					2.37

The results in Table 3 indicate that the utilization of AI-driven Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State was relatively low to average, with an overall mean score of 2.37. While a fair proportion of teachers reported incorporating AI-powered platforms in teaching STEM subjects (59.1%) and using AI-supported simulations or virtual laboratories (58.8%), the majority showed limited engagement with more advanced AI applications. For example, fewer teachers actively analyzed student learning patterns using AI analytics (only 43.3% agreed, while 56.4% disagreed), personalized teaching strategies based on AI-generated data (50.0% disagreed), or use gamified AI platforms to enhance engagement (54.3% disagreed). Similarly, collaboration among teachers to explore AI-driven strategies was modest, with just over half (53.3%) in agreeing

overall, the findings suggest that although sssteachers have begun integrating AI tools into assessment, feedback, and instructional delivery, their usage remains at a basic level. Advanced applications such as personalization, differentiated instruction, and analytics are less widely adopted, indicating the need for targeted training, improved infrastructure, and stronger institutional support to enhance the effective utilization of AI in STEM classrooms. This finding is supported by Bali et al., (2024) and Olabiyi and Chinedu, (2024)

Hypothesis Results

Research hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the usage of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools between school ownership by secondary school STEM teachers in Kwara State;

Table 4:

1. Independence sample of t-test showing the significant difference in the usage of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools between school ownership by secondary schools STEM teachers;

School Type	N	Mean	SD	T	Df
Private	97	22.2680	4.98856		
Public	229	24.3013	4.82056	-3.446	324

This result examined whether there was a significant difference in the usage of Intelligent Learning Systems and other AI tools between private and public secondary school STEM teachers in Kwara. The results show that private school teachers (N=97, mean=22.27, SD=4.99) reported lower usage of AI tools than their public-school counterparts (N=229, mean=24.30, SD=4.82). The independent samples t-test produced a value of $t(324) = -3.446$, indicating that the difference between the two

groups was statistically significant. This implies that public school STEM teachers make greater use of Intelligent Learning Systems and AI tools than those in private schools, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This finding was supported by Olabiyi and Chinedu, (2025).

Research hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in gender on the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers in secondary schools in Kwara;

Table 5

Independence sample of t-test showing is significant difference in gender on the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers

Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	Df
Male	124	24.3226	4.43113		
Female	202	23.3119	5.21925	1.795	324

The findings assessed whether gender influences the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers in secondary schools in Kwara. Findings revealed that male teachers (N=124, mean=24.32, SD=4.43) reported slightly higher usage of AI tools than female teachers (N=202, Mean=23.31, SD=5.22). However, the independent samples t-test yielded a value of $t(324) = 1.795$, which was not statistically significant. This indicates that the observed difference in mean scores between male and

female teachers is due to chance and is not real effect. Therefore, the null hypothesis was retained, suggesting that gender does not significantly influence the use of artificial intelligence among STEM teachers in the study area. These findings are consistent with those of Okorocho and Ugwunali (2025).

Research hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in subject discipline on access level to artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State

Table 6

Independence sample of t-test showing significant difference in subject discipline on access level to artificial intelligence by STEM

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	Sig.
Between Groups	462.051	2	231.025	9.585
Within Groups	7808.995	324	24.102	
Total	8271.046	326		

The findings tested whether there was a significant difference in the level of access to artificial discipline among STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State. The one-way ANOVA results revealed a statistically significant difference, $F(2,324) = 9.585, p < 0.05$. This indicates that teachers' access to AI tools varies significantly across discipline. Since the significance value (.000) was less than 0.05, the

null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, subject discipline has a meaningful influence on the level of access STEM teachers have to artificial intelligence in the study area. This finding is supported by Cobian et al., (2024).

Research hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in subject discipline on use of artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers;

Table 7

These results showing the one-way ANOVA significant difference in subject discipline on use of artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers;

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1077.979	2	538.989	25.264	.000
Within Groups	6890.957	323	21.334		
Total	7968.936	325			

These findings examined whether subject discipline has any influence on the use of artificial intelligence by STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State. One-way ANOVA results showed a significant difference, $F(2,323) = 25.264$, $p < 0.05$. This indicates that the use of AI tools by STEM teachers differs considerably across disciplines. Because the significance value (.000) is well below 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, subject discipline played a significant role in shaping the extent to which STEM secondary school teachers used artificial intelligence in the study area. These findings were supported by Makinde et al., (2025)

Conclusion

This study revealed that STEM secondary school teachers in Kwara State possess a moderate level of awareness of Intelligent Learning Systems (ILS) and other AI tools, as many are familiar with AI concepts and applications but show limited depth in understanding, confidence, and awareness of policy frameworks. Accessibility to AI technologies was also found to be moderate, with teachers having some access to digital devices, Internet connectivity, and AI-based tools. However, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical support, and financial barriers hinder full adoption. In terms of utilization, teachers

mostly engaged AI tools for basic instructional purposes, such as assessment, feedback, and lesson delivery, while more advanced applications including data-driven personalization, differentiated instruction, and learning analytics were less utilized. Hypothesis testing further revealed that public school teachers reported significantly higher usage of AI than private school teachers, while gender had no significant influence on AI usage. Importantly, subject discipline emerged as a significant factor affecting both the access to and use of AI, indicating disparities across STEM fields. Overall, these findings suggest that while foundation for AI adoption in STEM education exists, enhanced professional development, improved infrastructure, and stronger institutional support are crucial for advancing the effective and equitable use of AI-driven Intelligent Learning Systems in secondary schools.

Recommendation

1. The Ministry of Education and school authorities should provide structured professional development programs to enhance STEM teachers' knowledge and awareness of artificial intelligence.
2. Educational policymakers should ensure adequate provision of digital infrastructure and AI resources in secondary schools to improve STEM

teachers' access to artificial intelligence tools.

3. STEM teachers should be systematically supported through training and instructional guidance to facilitate the effective integration of AI technologies into classroom teaching and assessment.
4. Measures should be instituted to address disparities between public and private secondary schools, ensuring equitable opportunities for AI adoption by STEM teachers irrespective of school ownership.
5. Gender-sensitive interventions should be promoted to ensure both male and female STEM teachers are equally encouraged and empowered to utilize AI in their instructional practices.
6. AI tools and training programs should be designed to cater to all STEM subject disciplines, ensuring uniform access for teachers across various specializations.
7. Continuous professional development initiatives should target STEM teachers across disciplines to enhance their competence and confidence in applying AI effectively in teaching and learning processes.

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